

A Study of the Interaction between Thionyl Chloride and Substances containing the Reactive Methylene (-CH₂-) Group. Part III.

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The present work is a direct continuation of a previous work (Naik and Parekh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 137) the amides used being the substituted amides of acetoacetic acid and acetone dicarboxylic acid. The aim of this work is to show that the reactivity of the hydrogen atoms of the reactive methylene (-CH₂-) group, situated between two carbonyl groups, with respect to thionyl chloride, is in complete accordance with the hypothesis put forward (Naik, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1166, 1231; Naik and Avasare, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2592), viz., that the interaction of sulphur monochloride and a compound containing a reactive methylene group, depends upon the nature of the groups attached to the two remaining valencies of the carbon atom.

Thionyl chloride was made to react with following amides in presence of dry benzene.

(1) Acetoacetanilide, (2) acetoacet-*o*-toluidide, (3) acetoacet-*m*-toluidide, (4) acetoacet-*p*-toluidide, (5) acetoacet-*α*-naphthylamide, (6) acetoacet-*β*-naphthylamide, (7) acetoacet-(1:3:4)-xylylide, (8) acetoacet-(1:4:5)-xylylide, (9) acetone dicarboxyanilide, (10) acetone dicarboxy-*o*-toluidide, (11) acetone dicarboxy-*p*-toluidide, (12) acetone dicarboxy-*α*-naphthylamide and (13) acetone dicarboxy-*β*-naphthylamide.

When the solution was refluxed there was a copious evolution of hydrochloric acid with a change in the colour of the solution. The reaction was complete at the end of one hour.

The preparation of the substituted amides of acetoacetic acid was first attempted following the method described by Knorr (*Annalen*, 1896, 236, 75) which was subsequently discarded, yield being found extremely unsatisfactory. After some trials, the method used by Ewins and King (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 104) with some modifications was found to yield satisfactory results. For the preparation of the substituted amides of acetone dicarboxylic acid, the method

described by Besthorn and Garben (*Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 3439) was adopted. Amides (5 to 8) and (12 to 13) have been prepared for the first time.

The reaction in the case of substituted amides of acetoacetic acid (1 to 8) can be represented thus :

In the case of the substituted amides of acetone dicarboxylic acid (9 to 13), although more than two molecules of thionyl chloride were taken for every molecule of the substituted amide to give ample opportunity for the substitution of sulphoxide groups for all the hydrogen atoms in the two reactive methylene groups, reaction did not proceed to this extent and the product contained only one sulphoxide group, one hydrogen atom of each methylene group having been substituted.

The above constitution of the sulphur compounds follows from the following considerations :

(i) That the two hydrogen atoms are not supplied by the phenyl group follows from the reasons, (a) malondimethyl amide which does not contain such a phenyl nucleus reacts similarly with thionyl chloride to give a similar sulphoxide (Naik and Parekh, *loc. cit.*); (b) acetone dicarboxyanilide which contains two such phenyl groups also gives the same type of compound. On the supposition that the phenyl group is reactive, such a compound cannot be expected.

(ii) That the two hydrogen atoms are not those which are originally attached to the nitrogen atom of the -NH·R group for, (a) in the first place there is only one such hydrogen in a molecule of acetoacetanilide, while two hydrogen atoms have taken part in the reaction from the same molecule of acetoacetanilide; (b) a tertiary

amide like malondimethylphenylamide which does not contain such amido hydrogen. reacts under similar conditions with thionyl chloride to give a similar compound (Naik and Parekh, *loc. cit.*).

Now taking into considerations the three compounds (i) $\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{R}$, (ii) $\text{R} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{R}$ and (iii) $\text{R} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{R}$ it will be seen that the total negativity of the carbonyl groups with their attached radicles in the case of (i) is due to two groups, one of which $-\text{CO} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{R}$ is common to all the three compounds and the other, the acetyl group, which is more negative than the partly neutralised group $-\text{CO} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{R}$ which is present in (ii) and (iii). Again, the negative effect of the central carbonyl group in (iii) is divided between two adjacent methylene groups, so that the total negative effect on each of the methylene group is smaller than that on a single methylene group when linked as $-\text{CO} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO}-$ as in (i) or (ii). Hence it was expected that the two methylene groups in (iii) would be less reactive than the one in (ii), which in its turn would be less reactive than that in (i). From the facts stated above, it will be quite evident that such has actually been found to be the case. Whereas compounds of the type (iii) have given rise to sulphoxides of the type (II), compounds of the type (ii) and (i) reacted thus :

where R' is $-\text{CH}_3$ or $-\text{NH} \cdot \text{R}$ group. Reaction in the case of (i) however is much faster than in case (ii). Such behaviour is quite in accordance with the theory, already referred to above.

As compared with the sulphoxides of the substituted amides of malonic acid, these sulphoxides are not degraded into sulphides by boiling in benzene solution in presence of a catalyst like thionyl chloride, hydrochloric acid gas or iodine. They are also more stable towards moisture.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Acetoacet-a-naphthylamide.—Acetoacetic ester (13 g.) was mixed with *a*-naphthylamine (14 g.) in a conical flask with an air condenser, and the mixture was heated quickly to boiling and kept gently boiling for $1\frac{1}{2}$ minutes. On cooling, the amide crystallised out. It was filtered and washed with a mixture of benzene and light petroleum (1:1)

till it was free from the ester and the amine. It was then redissolved in hot benzene and filtered from the insoluble residue of the diamide which was also formed in the course of reaction. The filtrate was diluted with an equal volume of light petroleum (b.p. 50-60°) and allowed to cool. Acetoacet- α -naphthylamide crystallised out in pale red small needles, m.p. 108-09°. It is highly soluble in ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol, benzene and nearly insoluble in light petroleum. (Found: N, 6.12. $C_{14}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 6.16 per cent.).

Rest of the substituted amides of acetoacetic acid (6 to 8) were similarly prepared by condensing the respective amines with ethyl acetoacetate. The results are tabulated in Table I.

Acetone dicarboxy- α -naphthylamide.—Acetone dicarboxylic ester (10 g.) and α -naphthylamine (11 g.) were mixed together and heated in a sealed tube at 180° for 24 hours. The reaction mixture was diluted with about 500 c.c. of benzene when the amide separated out. It was filtered and washed with benzene till free from ester and finally with ether to remove amine. It was then recrystallised from hot alcohol as pale red granular mass, m.p. 165°. It is fairly soluble in glacial acetic acid, sparingly so in alcohol but insoluble in benzene, toluene, light petroleum or ether. (Found: N, 6.94. $C_{25}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires N, 7.07 per cent.).

Acetone dicarboxy- β -naphthylamide was similarly prepared from acetone dicarboxylic ester and β -naphthylamine. The results are tabulated in Table II.

Acetoacetanilide sulphoxide.—Pure dry acetoacetanilide (1.7 g.) was made to react with thionyl chloride (1.4 g.) in presence of dry benzene (30 c.c.). After refluxing for 1 hour, when the evolution of hydrochloric acid had nearly ceased, the clear solution obtained was concentrated and allowed to cool. Nothing separated out. Hence it was slowly added to a large amount of dry light petroleum (b.p. 50-60°) when a beautiful snuff coloured compound separated out. It was redissolved in benzene and separated by slow addition of light petroleum. It was then kept in an alkali desiccator till it was free from hydrochloric acid. It melts with decomposition to a thick black liquid at 90°, with a previous shrinking at 69°. (Found: N, 6.43; S, 14.26. $C_{10}H_9O_3NS$ requires N, 6.27; S, 14.85 per cent.).

All other sulphoxides were similarly prepared by treating the respective amides (1 mol.) with thionyl chloride (1 mol.) under similar conditions. The results are tabulated in Table III.

TABLE I.
New Substituted Amides of Acetoacetic Acid.

Name.	Formula.	Appearance.	Duration of heating.	M.p.	Analysis.	
					Found.	Calc.
Acetoacet- α naphthylamide	$C_{14}H_{13}O_2N$	Pale red short needles.	1½ min.	108-109°	N, 6.12	6.16 p.c.
Acetoacet- β naphthylamide	$C_{14}H_{13}O_2N$	White crystals.	1½	103-104*	N, 6.57	6.16
Acetoacet-(1:3:4)-xylylide	$C_{13}H_{12}O_2N$	White short needles.	1½	92°	N, 7.12	6.82
Acetoacet-(1:4:5)-xylylide	$C_{14}H_{12}O_2N$	Shining white tufts.	1½	96°	N, 6.95	6.82

TABLE II.

New Substituted Amides of Acetone dicarboxylic Acid.

Acetone dicarboxy- α -naphthylamide	$C_{25}H_{20}O_3N_2$	Pale red granular mass.	24 hrs.	165°	N, 6.94	7.07
Acetone dicarboxy- β -naphthylamide	$C_{26}H_{20}O_3N_2$	White needles.	24	207°	N, 6.71	7.07

TABLE III.
Condensation Products of Thionyl Chloride with Substituted Amides of Acetoacetic and Acetone dicarboxylic Acids.

Name.	Formula.	Appearance.	Shrinks at.	M.p. (with decomp.).	Analysis	
					Found.	Calc.
Acetoacetanilide-S	$C_{10}H_9O_3NS$	Snuff colour	69°	90°	S, 14.25 N, 6.43	14.35 p.c. 6.27
Acetoacet-o-toluidide-S	$C_{11}H_{11}O_3NS$	Pale brown	87°	110°	S, 13.79 N, 5.94	13.50 5.90
Acetoacet-m-toluidide-S	$C_{11}H_{11}O_3NS$	"	78°	93-94°	S, 13.70	13.50
Acetoacet-p-toluidide-S	$C_{11}H_{11}O_3NS$	Deep brown	87°	92-93°	S, 13.17	13.50
Acetoacet-o-naphthylamide-S	$C_{14}H_{11}O_3NS$	Pale brown	92°	112°	S, 11.34	11.72
Acetoacet-β-naphthylamide-S	$C_{14}H_{11}O_3NS$	"	82°	107°	S, 11.26	11.72
Acetoacet-(1:3:4)-xylylidide-S	$C_{13}H_{11}O_3NS$	"	90°	103°	S, 13.88	13.75
Acetoacet-(1:4:5)-xylylidide-S	$C_{13}H_{11}O_3NS$	Deep brown	97°	114°	S, 13.10	12.75
Acetone dicarboxyanilide-S	$C_{12}H_{11}O_5NS$	Pine rosy	140°	170°	S, 9.51	9.36
Acetone dicarboxy-o-toluidide-S	$C_{13}H_{13}O_5NS$	Pink	155-56°	174°	S, 8.45	8.64
Acetone dicarboxy-p-toluidide-S	$C_{13}H_{13}O_5NS$	Pink	186°	208-10°	S, 8.29	8.64
Acetone dicarboxy-α-naphthylamide-S	$C_{16}H_{15}O_5NS$	Greenish brown	137°	155°	S, 7.59	7.24
Acetone dicarboxy-β-naphthylamide-S	$C_{16}H_{15}O_5NS$	Crimson	185°	207°	S, 6.99	7.24

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